

Designing Social Media Marketing Strategies Targeting Generation Z for Subsidized Housing in Indonesia (A Case Study of Pt. Graha Putra Asido)

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ABSTRACT: PT. Graha Putra Asido, a housing company in Pematangsiantar, focuses on subsidized housing but lacks a targeted marketing strategy, with only 22.22% of their buyers being Generation Z despite this group dominating Indonesia's subsidized housing program. To avoid market loss and capitalize on Gen Z's significant social media usage, this research is done, aiming to propose appropriate marketing strategies tailored to Generation Z preferences and behaviors to enhance PT. Graha Putra Asido's market reach and engagement, using the P.O.S.T method and a touch on P.O.E.M Strategies. Through a mixed-method approach, including a market survey and key informant interviews, the study explores Gen Z's social media patterns, preferences, and the company's current marketing strategies. The research concludes with a comprehensive plan, including a Gantt chart, to achieve three main objectives by implementing targeted social media strategies, such as optimized posting schedules, platform-focused content, engaging visuals, influencer partnerships, and interesting campaigns tailored to Generation Z preferences.

KEYWORDS: Generation Z, Indonesia, P.O.S.T Method, Social Media Marketing, Subsidized Housing

I. INTRODUCTION

The rising cost of housing globally, including in Indonesia, presents significant challenges, particularly for younger generations. CEIC data reveals that Indonesian house prices increased by 1.7% YoY in December 2023, following a 2.0% YoY rise in the preceding quarter. Meanwhile, Wade (2024) highlights that Generation Z has the lowest average net worth compared to Millennials and Generation X. To mitigate these challenges, the Indonesian government has introduced various programs to assist low-income earners in purchasing homes.

One notable program is "Subsidized Housing," aimed at helping low-income individuals afford homes. Through initiatives like the Housing Financing Liquidity Facility Mortgage (FLPP), the government subsidizes a portion of the down payment and installment payments for homes, making them more affordable. These subsidized houses, typically smaller at around 36 square meters, come with lower mortgage rates and reduced down payments. Additional programs, such as the Cash Advance Assistance Subsidy (SBUM), further ease the initial financial burden by providing subsidies for down payments.

However, there are considerations for potential buyers of subsidized housing. These developments are often located on city outskirts, leading to longer commutes. Additionally, standardized designs may limit customization options. Despite these drawbacks, effectively marketing these homes is crucial for both companies and government programs. Social media, with its wide reach and cost-effectiveness, has emerged as a powerful marketing tool. In Indonesia, social media penetration is high, with 139.9 million users as of January 2024, making it a potent platform for targeted marketing campaigns.

The evolving social media landscape presents opportunities for marketing subsidized housing to Generation Z, who are known for their heavy social media usage. Studies reveal that a significant portion of Gen Z spends several hours daily on social media platforms like Instagram, WhatsApp, YouTube, and TikTok. Understanding their online behavior is key to reaching them effectively. Tailored content and targeted advertising on these platforms can maximize visibility among this crucial demographic.

Given these insights, it is imperative for housing companies like PT. Graha Putra Asido to adapt their marketing strategies to align with the preferences and behaviors of Generation Z. By leveraging social media marketing strategies (SMMS), companies can transform social media interactions into valuable marketing outcomes. This research aims to analyze and formulate the best

SMMS for subsidized housing companies targeting Generation Z, providing PT. Graha Putra Asido with recommended strategies to meet the changing needs of this generation.

II. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a mixed-method approach, combining a market survey targeting Generation Z in Indonesia to gather quantitative data on social media usage and its influence on housing decisions, with key informant interview from PT. Graha Putra Asido to gain qualitative insights into the company's social media marketing objectives. The research is structured to address the identified problem, define the research objectives, and design effective strategies for the company.

A. Framework

The research employs the P.O.S.T. framework to guide the development of social media marketing strategies. This framework is chosen for its structured and goal-oriented approach, ensuring that the research is cohesive and actionable. The P.O.S.T. framework consists of four key components:

1. **People:** Understanding the target audience, in this case, Generation Z in Indonesia, through a market survey to gather insights on their social media usage patterns, preferences, and housing needs.
2. **Objectives:** Setting clear and measurable goals by conducting a key informant interview with Mr. Andi Samuel Pardede, CEO of PT. Graha Putra Asido, to understand the company's marketing objectives and desired outcomes.
3. **Strategies:** Developing effective marketing strategies by analyzing the data from the market survey, focusing on Paid, Owned, and Earned media types to determine the most effective ways to engage Generation Z.
4. **Technology/Tools:** Selecting the appropriate technological tools to implement the strategies by assessing their importance and effectiveness through the market survey.

These four parts of the research will be conducted simultaneously, ensuring a comprehensive approach to developing optimized social media marketing strategies for PT. Graha Putra Asido. The P.O.S.T. framework's structured method ensures that insights are transformed into actionable recommendations, aligning with the company's goals and the target audience's needs.

B. Research Objects, Population, Samples, and Key Informant Selection

The research focuses on PT. Graha Putra Asido, chosen due to its active use of social media, emphasis on Generation Z, willingness to collaborate, alignment with research goals, and commitment to addressing the business challenge of engaging Generation Z in the subsidized housing market. The study targets Indonesian Generation Z (18-27 years old) social media users interested in purchasing housing properties in the future. Using purposive sampling, the research gathers data from a minimum of 200 participants who meet the specific criteria. Key insights for the company are provided by Mr. Andi Samuel Pardede, CEO of PT. Graha Putra Asido, ensuring comprehensive understanding and strategic alignment for the company's social media marketing efforts.

C. Data Collection Technique

The study collects the data in two ways: market survey and key informant interview. Market survey is done to collect a generalizable view of trends among Generation Z. Key informant interview is done to gain detailed insights into the company's goals and objectives.

1. **Market Survey :** The primary data collection for this research heavily relies on a market survey targeting Generation Z in Indonesia, aged 18-27. This survey aims to understand social media usage patterns, preferences, and housing needs among this demographic. The survey will gather quantitative data on various aspects such as demographics, social media platforms used, types of content preferred, and the influence of social media on housing decisions. To ensure the data's relevance and representativeness, purposive sampling will be employed. This non-probability technique involves selecting respondents who meet specific criteria: born between 1997-2006, Indonesian citizens planning to live in Indonesia long-term, social media users, and those interested in buying housing properties.
2. **Key Informant Interview :** In addition to the market survey, primary data will be collected through a key informant interview with Mr. Andi Samuel Pardede, the CEO of PT. Graha Putra Asido. This interview is crucial for understanding the company's marketing objectives, current strategies, and desired outcomes. Conducted via the Zoom platform, the interview will last approximately 30-40 minutes, ensuring an in-depth discussion. Mr. Pardede's unique position,

overseeing all divisions including marketing, makes his insights particularly valuable for this research. The interview will follow the SMART approach to ensure that the objectives discussed are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound. This dialogue will provide critical information on the strategic direction and goals of PT. Graha Putra Asido, aligning the research outcomes with the company's needs and enhancing the relevance and applicability of the proposed social media marketing strategies.

D. Data Analysis Technique

1. **Market Survey** : The data collected through the market survey will be analyzed using descriptive analysis. The following statistical measures will be applied:

- Frequencies and Percentages: To illustrate the distribution and proportion of responses to various questions.
- Mode: To identify the most frequently chosen options for multiple-choice questions, particularly for Likert scale questions.
- Mean: To determine the average response for Likert scale questions (1-5 scale).

This analysis aims to provide insights into the preferred social media platforms, types of content, and the influence of social media on housing decisions, helping to identify the most effective media types for engaging Generation Z, providing insights into the comparative effectiveness of paid, owned, and earned media, and identifying the importance of different technological tools in influencing Generation Z's interest in housing.

2. **Key Informant Interview** : SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) Analysis will be used to evaluate the marketing objectives obtained from the key informant interview, ensuring they are clear and effective. Following this, content analysis will be performed on the interview transcripts using:

- Open Coding: To categorize interview material into broad themed codes by collecting and grouping keywords according to their qualities and dimensions.
- Axial Coding: To develop relationships between categories and subcategories, creating more specific points to focus on.

This structured approach ensures a thorough understanding of the marketing objectives and their alignment with the company's goals.

3. **Utilizing Collected Data for Social Media Plan** : The insights gathered from the analysis will be utilized to create a comprehensive social media plan for PT. Graha Putra Asido.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. People

1. A majority of Generation Z have used social media for over two years, preferring evening use (5 PM - 9 PM) with additional peaks in the late afternoon and night.
2. Evening hours (5 PM - 9 PM) are the most popular period for social media use, with significant usage also in the late afternoon, late at night, early afternoon, and mid-afternoon.
3. Daily social media engagement is nearly universal in this generation, with most spending three to five or more hours per day.
4. TikTok and Instagram are the most popular platforms, while Twitter/X and YouTube are less used, and Facebook is the least used. However, Instagram is the preferred platform for housing information, followed by TikTok.
5. Entertaining content is the most preferred by Generation Z, underscoring the importance of entertainment in capturing and retaining their attention. Informative content is also valued, while interactive content is the least preferred.
6. Short videos (<3 minutes) are the most engaging type of content, highlighting the importance of being concise and quickly convey messages. Photos and texts/articles also hold significant value, while long videos and live videos or streams are less engaging. Adding to that, respondents preferred short videos explaining the program and facilities when learning about subsidized housing, followed by virtual tours and testimonials. On the other side, informative blog posts with FAQs are the least preferred type of content.
7. Generation Z engages significantly with brand content, with moderate to high levels of engagement and sharing being the typical behavior. They show a reasonable likelihood of using social media for communicating with real estate developers, but it may not be the most efficient channel for this purpose.

B. Objectives

Table 1. Interview Content Analysis

Question	Open Coding	Axial Coding
Q1.1	New to social media marketing	Current Social Media Marketing Strategy
	Using Facebook and Instagram	
	Previously relied on traditional advertising and referrals	
Q1.2	Content follows "PIE" standard (Promotion, Information, Education)	Content Strategy
	Providing information on current projects	
	Educating about subsidized housing and KPR	
Q1.3	Target demographic: 21 to pre-retirement	Target Demographic
	Social media as a channel to reach younger audience as primary users	
	Indirectly reaching older demographics through younger users	
Q2	No current tools or metrics for measuring social media success	Measuring Success
	Good audience response but not directly tied to sales	
	Sales through social media and marketplaces showing positive trends	
Q3	Social Media haven't increase sales significantly	Challenges and Goals
	Lack of information to work with influencers	
	Sales target: double to 200 units/year - Using personal accounts instead of professional influencers	
Q4	No fixed social media marketing plans yet	Current Planning and Objectives
	Higher engagement but lower conversion compared to referrals	
	Aiming to build brand awareness, especially among Gen Z	
Q5	Double annual sales from 100 to 200 units	Marketing Objectives
	Improve interaction-to-sale ratio	
Q6	Social media more focused for brand awareness, not direct sales	Role of Social Media
	Anticipated long-term impact	
	Consistent education and promotion to plant brand in audience minds	

Based on the interview, there are three primary objectives the company focuses on according to the interview, including :

1. Increase Asido's annual sales from 100 units to 200 units through targeted social media marketing campaigns by July 31, 2025

Table 2. Objective 1 SMART Analysis

S	Increase annual sales from 100 units to 200 units
M	Achieve a total of 200 units sold by the end of July 2025.
A	Implement targeted social media campaigns and promotions to attract potential buyers on suitable platforms with suitable content.
R	This goal aligns with Asido's objective to expand its market presence and increase revenue.
T	Complete by July 31, 2025.

2. Improve Asido's interaction-to-sales conversion ratio from 0.3% to 10% through enhanced engagement and call-to-action strategies on social media by July 31, 2025.

Table 3. Objective 2 SMART Analysis

S	Increase the interaction-to-sales conversion ratio from 0.3% to 10%.
M	Achieve a 10% conversion rate from social media interactions to actual sales.
A	Enhance engagement strategies and implement effective call-to-action techniques.
R	This goal is crucial for maximizing the efficiency of social media marketing efforts.
T	Achieve this ratio by July 31, 2025..

3. Increase Asido's brand awareness by 50% through a strategic content plan and influencer partnerships on social media by December 31, 2024.

Table 4. Objective 3 SMART Analysis

S	Increase brand awareness among the target audience (GenZ).
M	Achieve a 50% increase in brand mentions, shares, and followers across social media platforms.
A	Develop and execute content strategy suitable for target audience.
R	This goal is essential for building a strong brand presence and attracting potential customers.
T	Complete by July 31, 2025..

C. Strategies

1. Earned Media (people's reviews) is the most effective in gaining engagement from Generation Z. Paid Media (ads on social media) is also effective, while Owned Media (blogs and official posts) is moderately effective.
2. For PT. Graha Putra Asido to reach and engage Generation Z effectively, focusing on Earned Media and Paid Media would likely yield the best results. Owned Media can be used to complement these efforts by providing detailed and valuable information to potential customers.

D. Technology/Tools

1. Generation Z places high importance on visually appealing, well-organized, and well-edited content. They value organized social media platforms, regular content posting, and keeping up with current social media trends.
2. PT. Graha Putra Asido should invest in technological tools that enhance the visual appeal, organization, and consistency of their social media content.

E. Proposed Social Media Marketing Strategies for PT. Graha Putra Asido

Objective 1: Increase Asido's annual sales from 100 units to 200 units through targeted social media marketing campaigns by July 31, 2025

Strategies:

1. **Optimize Posting Schedule:** Post during peak times (5-9 PM, late afternoon, late night) to maximize visibility and engagement.
2. **Platform Focus:** Prioritize Instagram and TikTok to leverage their popularity among Generation Z.
3. **Content Type:** Create short (<3 minutes), engaging videos explaining the housing program and facilities.
4. **Interactive Campaigns:** Develop virtual tours and testimonial videos to provide an immersive experience.
5. **Earned Media:** Encourage customers to share reviews and testimonials on social media.
6. **Paid Media:** Invest in targeted ads on Instagram and TikTok to reach a broader audience.

Objective 2: Improve Asido's interaction-to-sales conversion ratio from 0.3% to 10% through enhanced engagement and call-to-action strategies on social media by July 31, 2025.

Strategies:

1. **Enhanced Engagement:** Use visually appealing and well-edited content to capture and retain attention.
2. **Call-to-Action (CTA):** Implement clear and compelling CTAs in posts and ads, such as "Book a Virtual Tour Now."
3. **Interactive Features:** Utilize Instagram Stories and TikTok challenges to boost engagement.
4. **Regular Content Posting:** Maintain a consistent posting schedule to keep the audience engaged.
5. **Customer Support:** Provide prompt and helpful responses to inquiries on social media.

Objective 3: Increase Asido's brand awareness by 50% through a strategic content plan and influencer partnerships on social media by December 31, 2024.

Strategies:

1. **Influencer Partnerships:** Collaborate with influencers who have a strong following among Generation Z.
2. **Strategic Content Plan:** Develop a content calendar with a mix of entertaining, informative, and interactive content.
3. **Hashtag Campaigns:** Create and promote branded hashtags to increase visibility and engagement.
4. **Visual Appeal:** Invest in professional graphic design and video editing tools.
5. **Trend Engagement:** Keep up with current social media trends and incorporate them into the content strategy.

By implementing these strategies, PT. Graha Putra Asido can effectively leverage social media to achieve its sales, conversion, and brand awareness objectives, tailored specifically to the preferences and behaviors of Generation Z.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study emphasizes the need to adapt social media marketing strategies to the unique preferences of Generation Z for subsidized housing. For PT. Graha Putra Asido, strategies include optimizing posting schedules, focusing on Instagram and TikTok, creating engaging short videos, and developing visually appealing campaigns to boost annual sales. Clear calls-to-action and interactive features aim to improve interaction-to-sales conversion ratios, while influencer partnerships and a strategic content plan are key for brand awareness. A Gantt chart provides a timeline for these activities, ensuring consistent efforts throughout the year. These strategies aim to maximize visibility, engagement, and conversions by aligning with Generation Z's social media habits.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Leveraging the strategies from this study can enhance social media marketing effectiveness for the subsidized housing industry. Utilizing platforms like Instagram and TikTok, favored by Generation Z, allows for engaging and relevant content. Short, visually appealing videos and interactive posts can drive engagement and visibility. Optimizing posting schedules to align with

Generation Z's online activity patterns maximizes reach and interaction. Implementing these recommendations can help industry practitioners and researchers develop more effective social media marketing strategies. However, companies should tailor strategies to their specific target markets for maximum effectiveness. Future research should increase geographic diversity among participants to capture a more comprehensive set of preferences and behaviors across Indonesia. Alternatively, focusing on specific regions can provide in-depth analysis. Expanding the age range to include younger Generation Z members (born 2007-2012) as they reach productive age will offer a fuller picture of this generation's preferences. Investigating digital literacy levels and external factors such as economic conditions and cultural influences will enhance understanding of how these factors affect social media marketing effectiveness, leading to more inclusive strategies.

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